

indicate credit card or identity theft (Neda, Leila & Ebrahim, 2012). Thus, the on-time detection of anomalies in a reliable, efficient and robust manner had been seen to be highly imperative.

2.2 How Anomaly detection works

The most effective anomaly detection approach focuses on the individual account holder. Different users quite naturally have different online banking behavior. Each account holder has a unique online banking fingerprint. Anomaly detection takes advantage of this fact combined with knowledge of online banking fraud attacks and general online behavior to determine if a specific online session is legitimate or has high risk of being fraudulent (Guardian Analytics, 2011). Guardian Analytics (2011) presented a simple breakdown of the process anomaly detection solutions use to detect suspicious activity for each individual account holder:

- i. Create and continually update a model of expected behaviour for each individual account holder.
- ii. Monitor all online banking for each individual account holder.
- iii. Analyze all individual account behaviour during an online banking session from login to logout – how they access their account, how they manage their accounts, the types of transactions they engage on, the frequency of activities, what kinds of activities take place during the same session, the type and amounts of payments, who the payees are, and much more.
- iv. By comparing individual or groups of activities in this online session to demonstrated patterns of normal behavior, determine if the session is legitimate or unusual, unexpected, or suspicious.

2.3 Credit Card in Online Transaction

In today's world, credit cards are used for purchasing goods and services via online transaction or physical card for offline transaction, even street vendors now accepts cashless payments. This development could be nailed to globalization. The increased use of internet technology for online shopping has resulted in a considerable increase of credit card transactions throughout the world (Patel & Kumar, 2013), along with the rapid advances of e-commerce. Credit card has become a convenience to all stakeholders in the financial economy. It is easy to carry and easy medium of payments while on the move and for online purchase (Dey & Sudha, 2018), and it might be physical or virtual. Despite all the benefits credit card serves, the rapid growth in the number of credit card transactions has led to a substantial rise in fraudulent activities. The rise in e-commerce has opened up new opportunities for criminals to steal credit card details and consequently commit fraud. According to Global Payments Report 2015, credit card is the highest used payment method globally in 2014 compared to other methods such as e-wallet and Bank Transfer. In the past couple of the years, credit card breaches have been trending alarmingly. Nilson Report also reported that the global credit card fraud losses reached \$16.31 billion in 2014 and it was estimated that it will exceed \$35 billion in 2020.

The development of efficient methods which can distinguish rare fraud activities from billions of legitimate transactions seems essential. Although, CCFD has gained attention and extensive study especially in recent years and there are lots of surveys about this kind of fraud (Samaneh Sorounejad *et al*, 2016).

2.4 Credit Card Fraud Detection Process

Credit card fraud being one of the major problems in the financial institutions such as banks, credit card industry etc., the goal of a detection system is to be able to detect fraud in the dataset in a real time manner, so as to reduce fraudulent transactions which cost hundreds of millions of dollars annually (Akshata & Sheetal, 2015). The main idea when detecting fraud is to firstly understand and identify the type of credit card fraud. There are various types of credit card fraud (both online and offline). Depending on the type of fraud faced by banks or credit card companies, various measures has been adopted and implemented curb these activities, but however, there is still a need for a more robust system in order to detect frauds more accurately.

A transaction is fraudulent if the transaction pattern and other properties (e.g. location, amount, etc.) do not conform or follow the regular pattern of that card dataset. A fraudulent transaction can be detected if the regular way in which the card owner uses his/her card isn't followed. The credit card dataset is used in training the ML algorithms. These algorithms are capable of learning and predicting without any human intervention. Consequently, the system will be able to recognize the patterns of every particular card holder and if any future transaction is fraudulent, the algorithm or model will be able to detect such fraudulent transactions.

2.5 Related Works

Detection of abnormalities in credit card online transactions has enjoyed quite number of attention and interest among researchers. A good amount of works in this domain are available in literatures. Navanshu *et al.* (2018), proposed a new collative comparison measure that reasonably represents the gains and losses due to fraud detection. They presented a cost sensitive method which is based on Bayes minimum risk using the proposed cost measure. The significance of their work was to find an algorithm to reduce the cost measure. An improvement up to 23% was obtained compared to other state of art algorithms. They used a real life transactional data by a large European company and the personal details in the data were kept confidential, the accuracy of the algorithm was gotten to be around 50%.

Fashoto *et al.* (2016) used a hybrid of K-means clustering with Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) and the Hidden Markov Model (HMM). They used K-means clustering to group together the suspected fraudulent transactions into a similar cluster. The output of this was used to train the HMM and the MLP, and later used to classify the incoming transactions. In their results, it was discovered that the detection accuracy of "MLP with K-means Clustering" is higher than the "HMM with K-means clustering" but the result is reversed for 10-fold cross-validation. In another work by Agrawal *et al.* (2015), they proposed testing credit card transaction for fraud using HMM, Behavior based technique and Genetic Algorithm (GA). HMM was used to maintain the record of previous transactions, Behavior based technique used for grouping the datasets while the GA was used for optimization, that is, calculating the threshold value.

Also, in the same year, Pooja *et al.* (2015) proposed simple K-means and Simple GA for fraud detection. They presented how K-means algorithm grouped the transactions based on the distinct attribute values, while GA was used for optimization because the increase in size of the input k-means algorithm produced outliers. Basically K-means produced clusters which were then optimized by the GA. In addition, Behera and Panigrahi (2015), proposed a hybrid approach to CCFD using Fuzzy Clustering and NN. Their work makes use of two phases. In phase one, they used a K-means clustering algorithm to generate a suspicious score of the transaction while in the next phase, a suspicious transaction was fed into NN to determine whether it was really fraudulent or not.

Esmaily *et al.* (2015) also proposed a hybrid of ANN and Decision Tree (DT). They used a two-phase approach. In the first phase, the classification results of DT and Multilayer perceptron were used to generate a new dataset which is the fed into the Multilayer perceptron, in the second phase, in order to finally classify the data. Their model promises reliability by giving very low false detection rate. Devaki *et al.* (2014) developed a CCFD using time series analysis. The parameters considered were transaction amount and transaction time. They used the periodic pattern in the spending behavior of a cardholder to detect the anomalies in the transaction with respect to the analyses of the past history of transactions belonging to an individual cardholder. Two levels of detection methods were used. The first level detects fraud by analyzing whether the new incoming transaction is fraud or not, using distance-based method, while in the second level, the next transaction was predicted by means of label-prediction methodology and compared with

Figure 2: Snapshot of the dataset

3.3 How the Algorithm works

Presented below is the pseudocode describing how the algorithm works. Figure 3 shows the flowchart for the steps involved in the process of anomaly detection, and the flow diagram of the model is depicted in Figure 4

Pseudocode 1: Pseudocode of the model.

```

// The following describes the how the algorithm works.
assign all network inputs and output
initialize all weights with small random numbers
repeat
  for every pattern in the training set
    present the pattern to the network
// propagated the input forward through the network:
  for each layer in the network
    for every node in the layer
      1. calculate the weight sum of the inputs to the node
      2. add the threshold to the sum
      3. calculate the activation for the node
end
end
// propagate the errors backward through the network
  for every node in the output layer
    calculate the error signal
  end
  for all hidden layers
    for every node in the layer
      1. calculate the node's signal error
      2. pupdate each node's weight in the network
end
end
  end
// calculate the Error Function
end
while ((maximum number of iterations <= specified)

```


$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{(TP+FP)} \quad (1.1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{(TP+FN)} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\text{Error Rate} = \frac{FN+FP}{TN+FP+TP+FN} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\text{False Positive Rate (FPR)} = \frac{FP}{FN+FP} \quad (1.4)$$

$$\text{Predictive Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TN+FP+TP+FN} \quad (1.5)$$

Figure 4: Flow diagram of the detection model

4.

FRAMEWORK

IMPLEMENTATION

MATLAB tool was the software framework adopted for the implementation of this work. MATLAB stand for Matrices Laboratory. It's a machine learning programming tool with interactive graphical user interface (GUI). It is a high-performance language for technical computing. The first step is to gather or collect the required transaction dataset and load into the simulator environment, as shown in Figure 5. Once the collected transaction datasets are imported into the workspace, input data and known output data are separated. What follow next is to create the training network/algorithm based on define type, structure and parameters, as depicted in Figure 6. This provides privilege to decide on; various network type MATLAB provided like feed forward, radial basis, activation function, internal structure of NN used like the number of nodes in the input layer, number of hidden layer and the number of nodes into the output layer, parameters values like weights, bias, delay.

As shown in Figure 7, Feed forward networks consist of a series of layers. The first layer has a connection from the network input. Each subsequent layer has a connection from the previous layer. The final layer produces the network's output. To ensure that the network is compatible with the problem we want to solve, we configure the network by arranging it. Usually the network is created with default values for its parameters, but one can change this either by reassigning. We used the default value of number of nodes, layers and hidden layer were used. 70% of dataset is used for training while 15% for validation and testing respectively. After the network has been configured, we initialized the weight and biases; these are adjustable network parameters which need to be tuned so that the network performance is optimized.

Figure 5: MATLAB environment

Figure 6: Creating the network

Figure 7: Showing the number of Hidden layers

Training the network, the pairs of input, output dataset is trained with the network created. Here, we created a two-layer feed-forward network, as shown in Figure 7 above. The network has ten (10) hidden layers with ten neurons.net = feedforwardnet(10); The network is trained for up to 1000 epochs to an error goal of 0.1 and then re-simulated.

```
net.trainParam.epochs = 1000;
net.trainParam.goal = 0.1;
```

To know when the training had converged, we set the parameter "show" before calling the training function

```
net.trainParam.show = 7;
```

In this case, the error value appeared on work space every "7" iterations like this:

```
TRAINB, Epoch 0/1000, MSE 0.5/0.1.
TRAINB, Epoch 7/1000, MSE 0.181122/0.1.
TRAINB, Epoch 14/1000, MSE 0.111233/0.1.
TRAINB, Epoch 21/1000, MSE 0.5189606/0.1.
TRAINB, Performance goal me
```

After training the network, we tested the performance on a test set. Figure 8 shows the training and testing section in the MATLAB environment.

Figure 8: The Train and Test section

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system was able to predict sample that are correctly classified and misclassified. The TP obtained is 92727 and the TN is 103. Figure 9 shows the classification table where the diagonal element represents the testing samples that are correctly classified, while other diagonal element represents the testing samples that were misclassified. Since we had highly imbalance classes with less than 0.2% of fraudulent activities, the classification accuracy is extremely high, which is 0.9993 (99.93%) as depicted in Figure 10. The Area under precision recall curve (AUPRC) of this model, as shown in Figure 11 is 0.5937, which indicates the need for improvement because a model with higher AUPRC indicate better performance. In others words, if AUPRC is equal to 1, it means the classification is perfect with 100% TP rate and no FP or TN. The overall performance of system is 79% while the validation is 99.98% with training accuracy of 100% with target output, when the neural system hidden layer was adjusted to 10. The graphical result of the training and testing of the model is shown in Figure 12, revealing the training accuracy, validation and performance respectively. The average mean Square error (MSE) that is used as the loss function, i.e. the average squared difference between the estimated values and target is 0.378as depicted in Figure 13. The best performance path is achieved when the validation is at 0.0031179 at first epoch, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 9: Classification table

Figure 12: Graph Results of Train and Test

Figure 13: The Train and Test section

Figure 14: NN Training plot performance

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work has contributed to the body of knowledge by successfully demonstrating comprehensively the effectiveness of Feed forward NN as a ML technique for anomalies detection, while generating few false alarms, in online credit card transactions, through implementation with MATLAB. It can be concluded that the model developed can detect fraudulent transaction from any datasets it is subjected to. The model is of greater accuracy and has least tolerant for raising false alarms when compared to some existing work on other models. However, future work can be carried out using real datasets, and comparing the effect of other ANN algorithms with another optimization algorithm.

